

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14845706

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Prevalence of Ocular Morbidity Among School Going Children in the Age Group of 6-16 Years

1. Main author **KHUBANI SNEHA JITENDRA**,
PHD student, GUJARAT UNIVERSITY, Ahmedabad, Gujarat, India
PORECHA EYE HOSPITAL, BAREJA

2. **Dr, Dipali. M. Purohit**

Department of cornea and refractive surgery, shri C.H. Nagri Eye Hospital, Ahmedabad, Gujarat, India

ABSTRACT

PURPOSE: - To determine the prevalence of ocular morbidity among school going children in the age group of 6-16 years.

Method: - In this population based prospective, cross-sectional study, 4057 children were examined from the random school selected from different areas of Bhuj, Ahmedabad, Modasa and Surendranagar from 6-16 years of age. A complete eye examination was conducted which includes detailed History, Visual acuity, Colour vision assessment, Refractive error measurement, Ocular deviation determination, Accommodation and Convergence and lastly Anterior and Posterior segments evaluation. The detailed evaluation was performed and studied by optometrist and ophthalmologist. If children required further evaluation, they were referred to the hospital. Detailed data analysis was performed.

Results: - A total number of 4057 students from different schools were examined, of whom 2137 were males, and 1920 were females. The commonest eye disorder was refractive error 10.59%(430) in which most common was myopic 66.51 (286), followed by astigmatism in which simple myopic astigmatism was 13.26 (57) and compound myopia was 11.2 (48) followed by mixed astigmatism 5.12 (22), simple hypermetropia 1.16%(5) and compound hypermetropic astigmatism 0.23%(1). Out of the spectacle usage, it was found to be present only in 35.11% (157) students, rest 64.88% (279) were not aware of the refractive error. Squint i.e. phoria was present in 0.74 % (30) and tropia was present in 0.2% (7), defective color vision was there in 0.5% (20); lids and adnexal disorders 0.07% (3). Amblyopia was 0.3 % (12), retinal condition 0.22 (9), corneal opacity 0.04 % (2) and rest i.e. Low vision, nystagmus, conjunctivitis and eyelid condition were 0.02 % (1). There were no students with congenital anomalies, congenital glaucoma or Vitamin A deficiency.

Conclusion: - The study concluded that most common ocular disorders were refractive error, squint and colour vision deficiency. This all disorders can easily be detected by routine eye examination and can be treated or prevented. Other ocular disorder are not in significant number but it can be diagnosed early with the help of vision screening program So, school screening program are the simplest and easy method to find the ocular morbidity.

Keywords: - Prevalence, ocular morbidity, School going children

INTRODUCTION

Vision is one of the most essential senses for daily activities. Poor vision can lead to suboptimal functioning of a person. It is very important to have good vision during childhood for proper development of the child, especially in the field of education. The learning potential of a child is affected by poor vision. ^[1]

Ocular problems, mainly leading to visual disability are important not because of the gross number but because of the number of blind years and its impact on the socio-economic condition of the community and country. The childhood blindness affects the entire family and many of them are left as street beggars in the poor countries. This has drawn the attention of World Health Organization's Vision 2020 program, which has included "Childhood Blindness" as one of its targets. There are an estimated 1.4 million blind children in the world. One million of them reside in Asia.

India has an estimated 320,000 blind children, more than any other country in the world.^[3] Estimated National Prevalence of Childhood Blindness/Low Vision is 0.80/1000 in India.^[4] Population based studies have estimated the prevalence of blindness as 1.25/1000 children in rural^[5] and 0.53/1000 children in urban areas^[6] in the age group of 5–15 years.

The available data suggests that there may be a tenfold difference in the prevalence ranging from as low as 0.1/1000 children aged 0–15 years in the wealthiest countries to 1.1/1000 children in the poorest.^[7] Considering the fact that 30% of India's blind lose their sight before the age of

20 years, the importance of early detection and treatment of ocular morbidity and visual impairment in young children is obvious.^[8] Inadequate infrastructure, funds, political will, National commitment and appropriate research are the barriers to eye care and blindness control.

Visual impairment due to refractive error is one of the important health disabilities in the school going children. Refractive error changes with the development of a child. Poor vision and inability to read due to refractive error have an impact on child's mental development and school performance. Visual disability in school children is preventable or treatable, but if not detected and treated in time can cause amblyopia and blindness in children.^[9]

Amblyopia is one of the causes of visual loss in children. Testing for amblyopia is one of the focus areas of many screening programs because of its prevalence, its effect on children and society, and the effectiveness of amblyopia treatment. Various studies indicate that amblyopia can be prevented by early detection of the causative factors in the early childhood and is most effectively treated in early childhood. The condition of strabismus or misalignment of the eyes can also be related to visual problems and therefore, there may also be a "critical period" after which permanent vision loss may occur without early intervention. Colour vision deficiency (CVD) is rarely included in screening protocols considering that congenital CVD are untreatable and not always considered as a disease. CVD testing should be included as part of screening programme as it can affect the development of a child.^[10]

Most of the available studies demonstrate that corneal and lenticular conditions are the predominant causes of blindness, whereas among children outside blind schools, refractive errors are important causes of visual impairment and blindness.^[11] In children of age range 5–15 years, the visual impairment is 6.4%, with refractive errors as the major cause.^[12] Every year, approximately half a million children add to this total (about one blind child every minute). The common causes of blindness in children are vitamin A deficiency disorders (VADD), refractive error, trachoma and hereditary / congenital diseases.^[13]

School Vision screening is crucial for early detection of ocular disorders in young children so as to prevent the risk of uncorrectable diminution of vision. The primary goal of paediatric vision screening is to detect children with unsuspected remediable visual conditions, to implement early treatment and reduce the impact that any untreated condition may have on their educational and social progress.^[14] So, in this study the school screening camp were conducted in the school to find the prevalence of ocular morbidity along with referring them to higher centre for further treatment.

Methods

In this population based cross-sectional randomized study, out of the various suburban school of Ahmedabad, Modasa, Surenderanagar and Bhuj including public and private schools, the schools were randomly selected whom the school screening camp was offered to Porecha Eye Hospital, Bareja. The time duration was from July 2022 to January 2024. Total 4057 students of 18 schools were included in this study out of which 2137 were male and 1920 were female respectively.

All participants were aged from 6 to 16 years and patients with age > 18 years, having any systemic pathology or any associated syndrome, non-compliance patient and if any previous ocular surgery was performed were excluded in this study.

The study was approved by AMC MET medical college committee, Ahmedabad and was conducted under the guidance of Porecha Eye Hospital Committee. Formal written consent was obtained from the Principal of the respective school on the behalf of the parents of the student studying in that particular school.

The detailed eye examination was performed by the senior optometrist and the other optometrist students of third year and interns which includes detailed history, visual acuity, colour vision assessment, refractive error measurement, ocular deviation determination, accommodation and convergence and lastly anterior and posterior segments evaluation.

Visual acuity (VA) was checked by using the Snellen's VA chart at 6 m, mainly English, Gujarati and illiterate E chart was used. In case if children VA was <6/6, then a pinhole test was performed to differentiate refractive errors from pathological conditions. If VA improved with pinhole, then the objective refraction i.e. both Autorefractometer, retinoscopy along with-it subjective refraction was performed.

For children already wearing glasses, visual acuity checked both with and without glass. If VA with glasses was not 6/6, the refraction was rechecked in such children. Cycloplegic refraction and post-mydratic (PMT) were not done in the school.

Color vision was done using an Ishiharas chart of 38 plates and if children did not read the 34 or more plates, then they were considered as colour vision deficient. Red-green deficiency was only assessed. Ocular deviation was examined by cover test, if strabismus was present after that the amount of deviation was recorded by using prism bar. Ocular movements were also checked by using Broad H test.

Accommodation and convergence insufficiency was examined by using the RAF rule.

Anterior segment examination including lids, lacrimal sac, conjunctiva, cornea, anterior chamber, pupil, iris and lens were done using a torch light and red reflex test with help of direct ophthalmoscope.

Undilated fundus examination was done for every child using a direct ophthalmoscope. In case if any children needing further assessment and management were referred to the hospital. Details such as name, age, gender, years of schooling, and name of the school were collected for each child 6 to 16 years old.

Results

A total number of 4057 students from different schools were examined, of whom 2137 were males, and 1920 were females (Table 1 and figure 1). Figure 4 shows the age wise distribution of students whom eye examination was performed.

The commonest eye disorder as shown in figure 2,3 and table 2,4 was refractive error 10.59%(430) in which most common was myopic 66.51 % (286), followed by astigmatism in which simple myopic astigmatism was 13.26% (57)and compound myopia was11.2% (48)followed by mixed astigmatism 5.12 % (22) , simple hypermetropia 1.16%(5) and compound hypermetropic astigmatism 0.23%(1). Figure 5 shows that of this spectacle usage was found to be present only in 35.11% (157) students, rest 64.88% (279) were not aware of the refractive error.

Figure 2 and table2 shows that Squint i.e. phoria was present in 0.74 % (30) and tropia was present in 0.2% (7), defective color vision was there in 0.5% (20); eyelids disorders 0.07% (3) . . Amblyopia was 0.3 % (12) and the lowest Visual acuity according to the age is shown in Table3. Retinal condition was 0.22 % (9), corneal opacity 0.04 % (2) and rest i.e. Low vision, nystagmus, conjunctivitis and iris coloboma were 0.02 % (1). There were no students with cataract, congenital glaucoma or Vitamin A deficiency.

Figure 1 Gender wise distribution of students

Figure 2 Distribution of ocular morbidity among school going children

Figure 3 Types of refractive error

Figure 4 Age wise distribution of students

Figure 5 Spectacles using among students

Table 1 shows gender wise distribution of students

Gender	no. of patient
Male	2137
Female	1920

Table 2: Prevalence of ocular disorders and their percentage

ocular morbidity	Percentage	no.of patient
refractive error	10.59	430
Conjunctivitis	0.02	1
Phoria	0.74	30
Tropia	0.2	7
corneal opacity	0.04	2
colour vision deficiency	0.5	20
Cataract	0	0
eyelid condition	0.07	3
Retinal	0.22	9
Normal	87.25	3540
Amblyopia	0.3	12
Nystagmus	0.02	1
LVA	0.02	1
iris coloboma	0.02	1

TABLE 3 lowest BCVA without correction

AGE	VISION
6	6/6
7	<6/60
8	<6/60
9	6/18P
10	6/36
11	6/36
12	6/60
13	6/36
14	6/36
15	<6/60
16	6/24

Table 4 Types of refractive error

Refractive error	No. of patient	Percentage
Myopia	286	66.51
hyperopia	11	2.59
SMA	57	13.26
SHA	5	1.16
CMA	48	11.2
CHA	1	0.23
MA	22	5.12

Discussion

Children in the school-going age group represent 25% of the population in the developing countries^[15]. To prevent ocular morbidity in children it is important to diagnose and treat ocular diseases as early as possible to prevent burden to the society. Vision testing in children is the process of detecting vision problems and to improve prognosis and reduce disability. Assessment of visual acuity in children is difficult due to the lack of awareness among the society.

In our study, total 4057 children were examined. There were 1920 were females and 2137 were males. overall ocular morbidity was 12.74 % among 4057 children screened which was in accordance with the study from rural area of Tanzania, Africa in which lower prevalence of 15.6% of ocular morbidity was reported in children aged 7-19 years and which was comparatively lower i.e. 20.2 % in the study of Vidya R, K.G. Kiran. Nepal *et al.* [16] found a lower prevalence of 11%. Prajapati *et al.* [17] in a Gandhinagar-based study reported a 13% prevalence. In the Kariapatti pediatric eye evaluation project initiated by Arvind Eye Hospitals, Nirmalan *et al.* [18] found a prevalence of 13.6%.

Refractive errors were the major cause of visual impairment accounting for 10.59 % ocular disorders among the age group of 6-16 years. These results were comparable with Gupta *et al.* [19] who also found refractive error as the most common disorder, with a prevalence of 22%. Das *et al.* [20] in Kolkata and Desai *et al.* [21] in Jodhpur also reported a similar prevalence of 25.11% and 20.8%, respectively. International studies conducted by Shrestha *et al.* [22,23] reported a similar prevalence of refractive error in their 2006 study (21.9%) and as well as their 2011 study (11.9%) in Nepal. Lu *et al.* [24] also found a comparable refractive error prevalence of 11.07% in Maqin county, China.

Internationally, lower prevalence of refractive errors (2.7-5.8%) has been reported among children of age 5-15 years from Africa, Finland, Chile and Nepal as compared to the present study. [25] These differences may be explained by the different diagnostic criteria used by different authors, racial or ethnic variations in the prevalence of refractive errors, different lifestyles or living conditions (e.g. reading, watching TV, or using computer/ visual display units, nutrition).

which most common was myopic 66.51% (286), followed by astigmatism in which simple myopic astigmatism was 13.26% (57) and compound myopia was 11.2 % (48) followed by mixed astigmatism 5.12 % (22), simple hypermetropia 1.16% (5) and compound hypermetropic astigmatism 0.23% (1). Of this spectacle usage was found to be present only in 35.11% (157) students, rest 64.88% (279) were not aware of the refractive error. Barriers to the use of corrective spectacles include: parental awareness of the vision problem, unaware of visual impairment because of sitting close to the blackboard, spectacle cost, and concerns that wearing glasses may cause progression, not availability of eye hospital in nearby rural areas of refractive error. Most of this impairment is caused by refractive error, for which treatment is simple and effective. So screening such students helps in the early detection of symptoms and timely interventions.

In our study, the second most common ocular morbidity was Squint i.e. phoria was present in 0.74 % (30) and tropia was present in 0.2% (7) i.e. 0.94 % which was nearly comparable with the study [26] Squint (1.4%) was the third most common cause of ocular morbidity among children in this age group. Strabismus was seen in 2.5% of the children. This was similar to a study done in Ethiopia, which had a prevalence of 1.8%. [27] Lower prevalence was seen in studies done in Ghana (0.9%), Warangal (0.42%) and Nainital (0.2%). [28,29,30]

This was followed by i.e. third most common was defective color vision which was there in 0.5% (20) which is similar to the prevalence of colour blindness observed in other studies i.e. 0.5% [31], 0.4 % [32] and 0.38 % [33]. It is also observed that the prevalence of colour blindness in boys is 0.6 % by this study which is significantly lesser than 3.16% rate observed in study done in Pune and Bhopal [34] and also less than the lowest rate i.e. 2 % observed in North America, Fiji and in certain Asian Indian tribes. [35]

In our study, the next common ocular morbidity was Amblyopia which was 0.3 % (12) and it is compared with Amblyopia was 0.41% in our study. Similar reports were submitted by

Wedner *et al.*^[36] (0.2%), Ntim Amponsah and Ofosu Amaah^[37] (0.2%), Kalikivayi *et al.*^[38] (1.1%),
Lu *et al.*^[39] (1.02%), Sapkota *et al.*^[40] (1.8%), and Preslan and Novak^[41] (3.9%).

The ocular disorders such as eyelids disorders was 0.07% (3), retinal condition 0.22% (9), corneal opacity 0.04 % (2) and rest i.e. Low vision, nystagmus, conjunctivitis and iris coloboma were 0.02 % (1). There were no students with cataract, congenital glaucoma or Vitamin A deficiency. These were not compared individually due to small number of cases.

Conclusion

The study concluded that most common ocular disorders were refractive error, squint and colour vision deficiency. This all disorders can easily be detected by routine eye examination and can be treated or prevented. Other ocular disorder are not in significant number but it can be diagnosed early with the help of vision screening program So, school screening program are the simplest and easy method to find the ocular morbidity.

Teachers and parents are the primary person who stays with child and observed them very closely. So, the visual acuity testing should be taught to the school teacher so they can evaluate at an early stage. The study helps to treat all avoidable cause of visual impairment and blindness. But this study was not conducted in various different areas of Gujarat, along with it doesn't include the preschool children, specially disabled child and also didn't categorize according to their socioeconomic status.

Acknowledgments: -

This study was supported by Porecha Eye Hospital, Bareja which comes under affiliation of blind's people association, Vastrapur.

The author would like to thank the PhD GUIDE Dr. Dipali M. Purohit for her guidance, support and cooperation. The author would also like to thank all the principal and families of the children who allowed me to conduct study on their children and also like to thank all the children who participated in this study and also for their cooperation. The author would also like to thank the students of Sheth Jamnabhai Bhagubhai BPA School of optometry for their cooperation, efforts and their assistance in this research work.

Source of Funding

Nil.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest

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